

Aloe pearsonii Pearson's Aloe

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Group: Monocot

Size: One metre in height

Distribution:

Pearson's Aloe is highly localised, occurring in the north-western corner of South Africa and the southern parts of Namibia in the Lüderitz district. It has a narrow distribution that is limited to the area between Kuboes in the South African Richtersveld National Park and the mining town of Rosh Pinah in southern Namibia. Its distribution falls within, and contributes to the biodiversity of, the Gariep Centre of Plant Endemism.

Importance:

Rising temperatures and prolonged drought in the Richtersveld (2015–2020) caused major die-offs of Pearson's Aloe, which has very low recruitment and grows extremely slowly. Overgrazing has intensified the decline, as livestock and wildlife now feed on this species due to the scarcity of other plants. Although valued medicinally and horticulturally, it remains difficult to cultivate.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 343.01 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 9.07 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 13.56 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 98.1% [Single: 86.8%, Duplicated: 11.3%]
BUSCO database: viridiplantae
Assembly N50: 1 121.75 kilobases
Contig number: 27 313

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